

VETERINARY SCIENCES

THE EGG MASS, SIZE AND SHAPE OF THE INDIGENOUS MACEDONIAN „KAMENJARKA“ HEN

Karova M.,

PhD Student, Faculty of Ecology FUTURA, Metropolitan University, Belgrade, Serbia

Urošević M.,

PhD, Full Research Professor, Center for Preservation of Indigenous Breeds, Belgrade-Zemun, Serbia, Faculty of Ecology FUTURA, Metropolitan University, Belgrade, Serbia

Mandić R.

PhD, Assoc. Prof., Center for Preservation of Indigenous Breeds, Belgrade, Zemun

Abstract

To date, Macedonia does not have any officially recognised chicken breed. For centuries, the primitive indigenous "kamenjarka" hen has been living in this region (Karova, Urošević, Mandić, 2023). Like all other primitive chicken breeds, the kamenjarka is characterised by small body size, extraordinary vitality and adaptability to different living environments. The hen is resilient to different climate conditions. It does not display particularly good production characteristics, since its body mass is only up to 2 kg (Karov, Kolev, 2021), and it lays up to 180 eggs per year (Karova, Urošević, Mandić, 2023).

The subject of this study is to determine the mass of the kamenjarka's egg and its basic morphological parameters: length (L), diameter (D) (Balackij, 2009), shape and shell colour. There is no data on the kamenjarka's egg parameters in the available scientific literature, hence the data presented in this study is the first to be published.

Over two months, the eggs of four laying hens were collected every day. The hens live in spacious boxes and have enough space for foraging and catching insects, but they are limited by a fence, since there are quite some predators around. In addition to what they find when foraging, they receive a mix of concentrated natural feed. The hens are in perfect health. During two months, 37 eggs were collected.

Keywords: "Kamenjarka", egg, egg mass, egg parameters, Macedonian heritage, poultry.

Material and approach

For determining the egg mass, an electronic scale "Galbac 927" was used. A digital Vernier caliper was used to determine the parameters L and D. The shell colour was assessed visually, and the egg shape was defined according to the model given by Balackij (2009).

Results

The egg mass varied between 36 g and 54 g (n=37). Considering the distribution of the egg mass frequency, we can see that the weight from 36 g to 43 g was represented by only one egg each (2,7%). The largest number of eggs, i.e. six, had a mass of 44 g (16,2%), while the second largest number of eggs weighed 49 g, represented by five eggs (13,5%).

Table 1

Distribution of egg mass frequency, g, (n=37)		
Weight (g)	Frequency	Percent
36	1	2.7
39	1	2.7
41	1	2.7
42	1	2.7
43	1	2.7
44	6	16.2
45	1	2.7
46	2	5.4
47	2	5.4
48	4	10.8
49	5	13.5
50	3	8.1
51	3	8.1
52	2	5.4
53	2	5.4
54	2	5.4
Total	37	100.0

According to Article 45 of the Law on the quality of agricultural products published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia No. 140 of 21.20.2010, chicken eggs are graded in four categories. The smallest eggs (S) weigh less than 53 g, medium eggs (M) weigh between 53 g and 63 g, large eggs (L) are from 63 g to 73 g, and extra large eggs weigh more than 73 g.

According to the official classification established by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy, the kamenjarka's eggs belong to the category of small eggs. Only two eggs weighed 53 g and 54 g, respectively, and hence are considered medium.

At this point, an inaccuracy in the definition of limit values has to be pointed out: The category of small eggs (S) is defined as 53 g and smaller, while medium eggs (M) are defined as weighing from 53 g to 63 g. Therefore, the question arises whether a 53 g egg belongs to category S or M? A category's minimum value has to differ from the next smallest category's maximum value. Hence, if the S category encompasses eggs of 53 g and less, the M category should start at 53,1 g, and the same principle should be applied to the limit values of all categories accordingly.

Picture 1: Electronic scale for measuring mass
(Picture: M. Karova)

The length (L) of the eggs ranged from the minimum value of 52,00 mm to the maximum value of 59,80 mm. The largest number of eggs, i.e. six (16,2%), was 55,00 mm, and the same amount of eggs was 59,80 mm long. We can see that, with regard to length, the variation interval is not very large.

Table 2

Length (mm)	Egg length, mm, L (n=37)	
	Frequency	Percent
52.00	1	2.7
52.50	1	2.7
52.90	1	2.7
53.00	2	5.4
53.50	3	8.1
54.00	3	8.1
54.50	1	2.7
55.00	6	16.2
55.90	1	2.7
56.00	6	16.2
56.50	2	5.4
57.00	3	8.1
57.50	1	2.7
58.00	5	13.5
58.80	1	2.7
Total	37	100.0

Picture 2: Measuring egg length (L)
(Picture: M. Karova)

The diameter of the eggs (D) was measured at the maximum width (n=37). The variation interval of the measurements (mm) is relatively small, spanning from 39,00 mm to 42,00 mm. Therefore, we can state that the egg width is a rather constant value. The largest number of eggs, i.e. 16, had a diameter of 40,00 mm (43,2%). 11 eggs (29,7%), the second largest number, had a diameter of 41,00 mm.

Table 2

Width (mm)	Frequency	Percent
39.00	4	10.8
39.50	1	2.7
39.60	1	2.7
39.80	1	2.7
40.00	16	43.2
40.10	1	2.7
41.00	11	29.7
42.00	2	5.4
Total	37	100.0

As for the shell colour, the shell of all 37 eggs was of dirty white colour. The egg shape was determined according to Balackij's model (2009) .

Table 3

extended egg-shaped	egg-shaped	pear-shaped	ellipsoid
23 (62,16%)	12 (32,43%)	1 (2,70%)	1 (2,70%)

As we can see from Table 3, there is no doubt that the largest number (62,16%) of the Macedonian kamenjarka's eggs are extended egg-shaped, followed by egg-shaped. Pear-shaped and ellipsoid egg shapes are rare.

Table

Parameter	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Deviation
Weight (g)	37	36	54	47.41	0.69	4.20
Length (mm)	37	52.00	58.80	55.47	0.29	1.81
Width (mm)	37	39.00	42.00	40.27	0.12	0.75

Conclusion

From a general point of view, variation intervals are not large and standard deviation is represented by small values. The indigenous kamenjarka chicken breed, which is being raised to this day with next to no human interference, lays eggs of quite standardised shape and mass.

Due to the relatively small sample in this study, similar studies should be conducted, observing the morphological characteristics of the eggs during the entire laying season and encompassing, if possible, a larger number of hens.

References

1. Balackij N.N. 2009. Gnezda ptic, juga zapadno-sibirske ravni. Nauka centar. (Н.Н. Балацкий. 2009. Гнезда птиц, юга западно-сибирской равнины. Наука центар)
2. Karov I., Kolev G. 2021. Makedonska autohtona kokoška – kamenjarka. Macedonian Rock Chicken. Zbornik predavanja trećeg simpozijuma „Zaštita agrobiodiverziteta i očuvanje autohtonih rasa domaćih životinja“ Zbornik radova, Dimitrovgrad, pp. 141–142.
3. Karova M., Urošević M., Mandić R. 2023. The duration of the Egg Laying Season of the indigenous „Kamenjarka“ Hen. Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science No 116, pp. 81–83.
4. Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia, No 140, 21.10.2010.